

Reverse Logistics and Customer Referral of Paint Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between Reverse Logistics and Customer Referral of Paint Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State. Reverse logistics was operationalized into two dimensions: product return and product recycling. This study adopted a survey research design. The population for this study consists of 7 functional paint manufacturing firms in Rivers State as documented in Nigerian Directory. The researcher sent five (5) copies of the research questionnaire to senior staff of each of the 7 paint manufacturing firms, making a total of thirty-five (35) respondents. The Spearman Rank Order Correlation coefficient with the aid of SPSS 25.0 version was used to establish the relationship among the empirical referents of the dimensions of the predictor variable and the criterion variable. From the data analysis, it was revealed that reverse logistics have positive and significant relationship with Customer Referral of Paint Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State. Based on this finding, the study concludes that Paint Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State should adopt reverse logistics practices such as; product return and product recycling practices to achieve customer satisfaction and hence referral.

Keywords: Reverse Logistics, Product Return, Product Recycling, Customer Referral

INTRODUCTION

In today's world organisations are increasingly managing the return of goods from the consumer to the supplier. This is encouraged for value recovery, environmental protection and sustainable development. At the same time, higher competition among organisations and customer protection laws allow customers to return products free of charge if they are not satisfied (Brito & Dekker, 2003; Krumwiede & Sheu, 2002; Lee, 2002). Reverse logistics involves the management of the recovery of products once they are no longer desired or can no longer be used by consumers to obtain an economic return through reuse, remanufacturing or recycling (Rubio, 2017). Efficient logistics operations are pivotal to manufacturing firms, including those in the paint industry. Reverse logistics, which encompasses the processes involved in the return of products from consumers back to manufacturers, has emerged as a critical area of focus. This includes activities such as returns management, recycling, remanufacturing and waste disposal. Optimization of reverse logistics not only mitigates environmental impact but also enhances operational efficiency and cost-effectiveness (Rogers & Tibben-Lembke, 2017).

Reverse logistics is an important component of supply chain management and useful for recovering value from the returned goods (Cater & Ellarm, 1998). Reverse logistics is the building block of the supply chain management and a strategic tool to optimize the global Supply Chain (Sathish & Jayaprakash, 2017). According to Roger and Tibben-Lembke, (2017) Reverse Logistics is the process of planning, implementing and controlling the efficient, cost-effective flow of raw materials, in-process inventory, finished goods and related information from the point of consumption to the point of origin for the purpose of recapturing value or proper disposal. Reverse logistics is based on five principles, which are: returns, recall, repair, repackaging and recycling (Malmgren & Larsson, 2020). These principles help elaborate on what a reverse logistics system is expected to do. From the above definitions, it can be seen that reverse logistics is basically the movement of materials from the customer side (downstream of supply chain) to the manufacturer and supplier side (upstream of supply chain) (Damian-Okoro & Hamilton-Ibama, 2024). Ashish, Agarwal & Sharma (2020) examined various practices within reverse logistics and highlighted the importance of

optimization in the efficient management of returns and the recapture of value from returned products. Each dimension is interlinked and required for effective managing approach to reverse logistics processes and satisfying customer.

Referral marketing, also known as word-of-mouth marketing, is a powerful strategy where satisfied customers refer others to a business based on their positive experiences. It leverages the trust and credibility inherent in personal recommendations, making it a highly effective and cost-efficient way to acquire new customers (Hanssens, 2015). Susskind (2017) defined customer referral as "communication in which people share their evaluations and assessments on service providers and products. Reverse logistics plays a pivotal role in shaping customer satisfaction vis a vis customer referral. In the context of paint manufacturing firms, this involves the management of returned, damaged, or obsolete products. An efficient reverse logistics strategy can lead to a seamless customer experience by offering convenient and transparent returns, warranty services and repairs. However, Ogunleye (2013) said the product return experience can influence customer perception of the service they receive. When customers are not satisfied with the product due to the product did not meet their needs and expectations, the product will be returned and a return may mean customer dissatisfaction.

However, satisfaction is dynamic; it may evolve and be affected by a variety of factors. A referral is primarily introducing someone to one or more providers of the service they are seeking and enabling them to make their own choice. Referrals can be regarded as an informal communication from a customer, directed at others about the usage or characteristics of particular services or a related service provider (Gremler, Gwinner & Brown, 2021). People are more likely to trust recommendations from friends or acquaintances than traditional advertising, as they perceive them as unbiased and genuine (Godes & Mayzlin, 2019). Positive experiences with a product or service increase the likelihood of customers referring others, while negative experiences can lead to negative word-of-mouth and damage to the brand reputation (Grewal, Roggeveen & Nordfalt, 2020). Referral programs form an attractive method to acquire new customers, as they are cost effective to run and provide access to prospective customers that traditional marketing programs may not effectively reach (Berman, 2016), and most importantly, customers acquired through referral programs can be more valuable than customers acquired through other methods (Schmitt, Bernd & Van den Bulte, 2011).

The paint industry is one of the growing industries in the city of Port Harcourt compared to other industries. Most paints manufacturing firms have been responding to the changing business environment by making decisions on the need to change their operations in the light of the complexities emanating from the environment (Adeyemi, 2000). Given the paradigm shift from the sellers' market to buyers' market, efforts have been directed by most paint manufacturing firms towards sustaining hard-core loyal customers and satisfying them. Specifically, managers of paint manufacturing firms in the Rivers State of Nigeria are under pressure of producing quality paints at reduced cost, coupled with an array of requirements that ought to create value for customers and stakeholders and ultimately reap success. Moreover, the need for paint manufacturing firms to increase their revenue, make profits and grow their businesses amid frenetic competition has become urgent. Hence, it is expected that enterprise managers in the paint manufacturing sector can navigate these challenges and run their businesses successfully if they improve on their Reverse Logistics practices to enjoy customer referral. The need for this relationship is absolutely pertinent as long as business longevity is concerned (Jurah, 2015). It is against this backdrop, that this study is designed to explore the relationship between Reverse Logistics and customer referral of paint manufacturing firms in Port Harcourt.

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework of the Relationship Between Reverse Logistics and Customer Referral of Paint Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State.

Researcher's conceptualization from literature review, 2025.

Theoretical Foundation: Institutional Theory

The concept of institutional theory is a common theory used to explain how organisations plan, design and implement strategies (Adebanjo, 2017). The institutional theory posits that organizations operates with a certain guiding boundary. The guiding boundary is the framework which are the policies, structures and routine practices regulating behaviour in the organization (Laosirihongthong, 2018). Reverse logistics is used by organisations to be responsive to product returns from customers' whiles maintaining a good relationship with the customer (Coşkun, 2018). Information collected from the reverse flow can be used to improve design, manufacturing, packaging and pricing of the product hence contributing to quality and flexibility. Recent research has indicated that customer's perception is changed when they experience delay in product delivery, price and product availability. Organisations practice reverse logistics because customers value friendly relationships (Taylor, 2016). By leveraging their unique resources and capabilities in this area, paint manufacturers can enhance efficiency, reduce costs and increase customer satisfaction, ultimately leading to sustainable business success.

Concept of Reverse Logistics

Reverse logistics refers to the process of performing logistics activities in the opposite direction, from the point of consumption back to the point of origin. According to Rogers and Tibben-Lembke (1998; 2002) reverse logistics is the movement of products in the opposite direction of a forward flow to create or recapture the value of products when possible or otherwise proper disposal. It is also known as aftermarket logistics, return logistics or aftermarket supply chain. The main objective of reverse logistics is to recover lost value. Reverse logistics refers to the return of products to sellers or manufacturers due to their problems or consumer dissatisfaction (Kok et al., 2016). According to Rao, Lee & Connelly (2018), consumers might want to return or exchange the products when consumers are not satisfied with the product. Hence, a clear return policy should be able to guarantee the product quality being purchased and make consumers feel security when they receive wrong items.

Reverse logistics is an essential feature of manufacturing organizations for strategic marketing and effective customer relationship management (Autry, Daugherty & Richey, 2001; Krumwiede & Sheu, 2002; Mukhopadhyay & Setaputra, 2006). In the same line, the Reverse Logistics Executive Council (2012) states that reverse logistics refers to the process of planning, implementing and controlling the efficiency and the cost effectiveness of the flow of raw materials, work in process, finished products and all related information, from the point of consumption to the point of origin in order to recapture value or to offer an appropriate disposal. Impliedly, reverse logistics primarily helps to increase supply chain efficiency via cost reduction strategies while simultaneously reduce substances that threatens environmental sustainability.

There are diverse reverse logistics practices adopted by manufacturing companies. Some researchers (Eshikhati, 2014; Ndung'u & Moronge, 2017) have identified remanufacturing, return, reuse, repackaging, recycling and disposal as the commonly adopted reverse logistics practices undoubtedly, these practices have some perceived benefits to organizations. Laosirihongthong, Adebanjo and Tan (2013) articulate that practicing reverse logistics helps organizations to follow stringent legal regulations which prevent them from incurring penalties related to non-compliance. Salim (2016) further indicates that organizations that adopt reverse logistics are considered socially responsible due to their consistent use of environmentally friendly activities. Thus, the integration and subsequent application of key reverse logistics activities makes an organization ecologically friendly. This enhances the reputation and goodwill of organizations which according to Dowling (2004) is a significant determinant that gives firms the competitive edge over their rivals. A properly managed reverse logistics process also minimizes logistics cost and improves the profitability of organizations (Bernon, et. al., 2011). The practices of reverse logistics adopted by Ndung'u & Moronge, (2017) is considered the most suitable for this study.

Concept of Product Return

Product return is the recipient of shipped or distributed products for further manufacturing or recycling (Alshura & Awawdeh, 2016). Product Return refers to the process of exchanging a product if it seems faulty to the customer. Product returns include products that are returned without fulfilling some or all of the claimed functionality and where a buyer or retailer returns a product to the manufacturer with a demand for a refund or replacement (Daugherty, Myers & Richey, 2002; Lee 2002; Richey et al. 2004). This policy should be smooth and trouble-free as it will earn the firm positive review and customer's trust, which will be helpful to grow the business.

Return management is a critical aspect of reverse logistics, it involves handling and processing products that have

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been returned by customers (De Oliveira et al., 2021). Some of the products commonly involved in return management in reverse logistics include, products that customers have returned to the retailer or manufacturer due to defects, damages or dissatisfaction (Malmgren & Larsson, 2020). Another reason parts or products are returned is because of defective products; these products do not meet quality standards or specifications and need to be returned to the manufacturer for repair or replacement (Bernon et al., 2018).

Concept of Product Recycling

Recycling involves the breakdown of an already used product or waste product into manageable components and reprocessed into its original or new form (Agrawal & Singh, 2020). Parallel to this description, recycling can be defined as the process whereby materials that are earmarked as waste are recovered from the environment, sorted out and reprocessed for the purpose of reusing the processed materials as inputs or finished product (Global Recycling Network, 2008). Recycling as a key reverse logistic component is commonly known in Rivers State but less practiced by manufacturing companies, with paint manufacturing firms not precluded. Another important practice is to integrate well-documented policies of recycling into their operations; firms can also create awareness by putting recycling signs on their packaging (Laosirihongthong et. al., 2013) and give appreciated incentives to customers who return used products for recycling.

Baker, (2008) defined recycling as the process to change waste, used or returned products into new products to prevent waste of potentially useful materials, reduce the consumption of fresh raw materials, reduce energy usage and reduce air pollution. Ellram (2006) noted that the process of recycling as well as reusing the recycled material proves to be advantageous for many reasons as it reduces amount of waste sent to landfills, conserves natural resources, saves energy, reduces greenhouse gas emissions and helps create new jobs. Recycled materials can also be converted into new products that can be consumed again such as paper, plastic and glass (Zhu, 2008). To an individual firm, this translates to cost savings and new streams of income (Blumberg, 2005), which should improve the profitability. Additionally, a focus on sustainability through recycling and refurbishment can appeal to environmentally conscious consumers, thereby enhancing overall satisfaction and loyalty (Agrawal & Singh, 2020).

Concept of Customer Referral

A referral is primarily introducing someone to one or more providers of the service they are seeking and enabling them to make their own choice. Referrals can be regarded as an informal communication from a customer, directed at others about the usage or characteristics of particular services or a related service provider (Gremler, Gwinner & Brown, 2021). Referral in marketing refers to a method of spontaneously promoting a business's products and services to new customers by word of mouth (Monica, 2008). Word of mouth (WOM) is an important marketing phenomenon and its use as a customer acquisition method has started to attract renewed interest (Godes & Mayzlin 2009; Iyengar, Van den Bulte & Valente, 2010). According to Eze and Chong, (2015) word of mouth communication channel is adjudged to be very trustworthy and more unbiased, since it is not generated by the companies but rather by the consumers who will be very objective and unbiased in their assessment. Referral marketing is a powerful strategy for acquiring new customers and driving business growth and most importantly, customers acquired through referral programs can be more valuable than customers acquired through other methods (Schmitt, Bernd & Van den Bulte, 2011). By leveraging the trust and credibility of satisfied customers, businesses can tap into the vast potential of word-of-mouth recommendations to expand their customer base and enhance brand reputation.

Empirical Review

Reverse Logistics and Customer Referral

Bilqis, Sulaimon & Kayode, (2019) explores reverse logistics activities such as product return, reuse of materials, and waste disposal impacts on the management of waste products in the Nigerian manufacturing companies. Using a cross-sectional survey research design, 300 staff of selected manufacturing firms that deal with waste product were selected in Lagos and a well-structured and validated questionnaire was administered. From this, 250 copies were returned, while 246 were valid for the purpose of analysis. Data generated were analysed using descriptive statistics, analysis of variance test of significance and Friedman rank test. Their findings revealed that reverse logistics activities arising from return of goods may be very important in the development of efficient and effective management of waste products in Nigeria manufacturing firms. The results also indicated that reverse logistics is highly significant in achieving organizational goals, company's future success, the functioning of a manufacturing company and strategically positioning of the company. The study therefore recommended the need for a growing focus on various sections of reverse logistics processes in waste products' management of manufacturing companies in order to for them to achieve organizational goal and enhance sustainable business performance.

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Damian-Okoro & Hamilton-Ibama, (2024) examines the relationship between reverse logistics practices and marketing performance of registered breweries in South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Reverse logistics practices were operationalized into three dimensions: recycling, reuse and remanufacture. On the other hand, marketing performance was measured in terms of customer satisfaction and customer retention. The study adopted cross-sectional research design. The population of the study was six (6) registered breweries in South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria as obtained from yellow page (2023). The research adopted a census study because of the small size of the study. However, 10 managers were drawn from each of the six (6) registered breweries making sixty (60) managers as respondents for the study. Data were collected through semi - structured questionnaire. Inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the hypotheses. These analyses were done with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 23.0). From the data analysis, it was revealed that reverse logistics practices have positive and significantly relationship with marketing performance of registered breweries in South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Based on this finding, the study concludes that the reverse logistics practices employed here are relatively good in the registered breweries firms especially in a competitive environment like South-South geopolitical zone. Somuyiwa and Adebayo (2014) conducted an empirical study of the effect of reverse logistics objectives on economic performance of food and beverages companies in Nigeria. With data collected from both primary and secondary sources of data on food and beverages companies, analysis was done using inferential statistical analysis. The results showed that the companies have been effective in using reverse logistics to reduce total logistic cost, improve customer satisfaction, enhance competitive advantage and in minimizing the environmental impact of returns as well as recovery of materials for re-use. Based on the findings of the study it was recommended that for reverse logistics systems to be successful, top management must guide and support the implementation and also recognize the fact that, reverse logistics cannot be managed in isolation.

Product Return and Customer Referral

Lemon, (2017) conducted a study on the impact of returned policies on customer satisfaction and loyalty. The research adopted a mixed-method study involving both quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews. They surveyed customers from multiple retail sectors and followed up with in-depth interviews to gather insights into customer experiences with different return policies. The study found that lenient return policies, such as no-questions-asked returns, product replacement and extended return windows, significantly enhanced customer satisfaction and loyalty. Customers valued the flexibility and security these policies provided, leading to increased trust in the retailer.

Nguyen (2018) conducted a study to investigate customer expectations and perceptions of fairness in return processes. The research conducted a cross-sectional survey of customers from various retail backgrounds. The survey assessed customer expectations before making a return and their perceptions of the fairness and transparency of the return process, the findings revealed that, customers who perceived the return process as fair and transparent reported higher satisfaction levels. Key aspects influencing perceptions included clarity of return policies, ease of the return process, product replacement and the respect shown by customer service representatives.

Petersen and Kumar (2015) conducted research on how return experiences impact overall customer satisfaction and retention. The study utilized a longitudinal survey approach, tracking customer satisfaction levels before and after return experiences and analyzed data from customers of a major online retailer, focusing on variables such as return process ease, refund speed and customer service quality during the return. The findings analysis showed that a smooth and efficient return process could significantly mitigate dissatisfaction caused by a defective or unwanted product. Quick refunds and courteous customer service were particularly influential in maintaining customer loyalty.

Product Recycling and Customer Referral

Yang & Johnson (2017). Conducted a study on the impact of Recycling Practices on Customer Satisfaction in the Hospitality Industry, they examined how different waste management strategies influenced customer satisfaction in hotels and restaurants. The research used surveys and interviews to collect data from guests and found that establishments with more visible and user-friendly recycling options reported higher satisfaction ratings among their clientele. The study suggests that integrating sustainable waste practices can serve as a differentiator in competitive hospitality markets. Li & Zhang (2019) Conducted a study on Retail Recycling Facilities and Customer Experience, they explored how the presence and quality of recycling facilities in retail environments affect customer satisfaction. Using a mixed-methods approach, including customer surveys and observational studies, they concluded that the convenience and ease of use of recycling facilities directly contribute to a positive shopping experience and overall customer satisfaction.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a survey research design which measured two variables; independent variable and dependent variable. The populations for this study consist of 7 functional paint manufacturing firms in Rivers State as documented in Nigerian Directory. The researcher sent five (5) copies of the research questionnaire to each of the 7 paint manufacturing firms, making a total of thirty-Five (35) respondents. The Spearman Rank Order Correlation coefficient with the aid of SPSS 25.0 version was used to establish the relationship among the empirical referents of the dimensions of the predictor variable and the criterion variable.

Table 1 Administration and Survey Results

Distribution	35 distributed copies (100%)
Retrieved copies	35 copies retrieved (100%)

Source: Survey Data, 2025

RESULT

Analysis on Reverse Logistics

Table 2 Response Rates and descriptive statistics for Product Return

Product Return	SA [5]	A [4]	U [3]	D [2]	SD [1]	Mean	Std.
How often do customers return products	15	7	6	2	5	4.15	0.647
How would you rate the efficiency of the current product return process	9	16	3	4	3	3.86	1.027
What challenges do you face in managing product return	14	7	10	2	2	3.59	1.175
What improvements can be made to the product return process	10	10	7	5	3	3.88	1.247

Source: Research Survey Data, 2025

Table 2 illustrates the response rates and frequency for Product Return measured on a 4-item instrument and scaled on a 5-point Likert scale.

Table 3 Response Rates and descriptive statistics for Product Recycling

Recycling Disposal	SA [5]	A [4]	U [3]	D [2]	SD [1]	Mean	Std.
Are you aware of the company's recycling program	19	14	0	0	2	3.88	1.247
How effectively does the company manage recycling of unused paint products	13	9	11	2	0	3.85	1.085
How would you rate the ease of using the recycling and disposal program	18	11	4	0	2	2.85	1.106
How important is it to you that companies offer a recycling and disposal program	14	10	0	9	2	4.27	1.066

Source: Research Survey Data, 2025

Table 3 illustrates the response rates and frequency for Recycling Disposal measured on a 4-item instrument and scaled on a 5-point Likert scale.

Table 4 Descriptive statistics for Reverse Logistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Product Return	35	3.59	4.15	3.8596	.27924
Product Recycling	35	2.85	4.27	3.0877	.94837
Valid N [List wise]	35				

Source: Research Survey Data, 2025

Table 4 above illustrates the descriptive statistics for Reverse Logistics; Product return and Recycling with mean scores of 3.3895 and 3.0877 respectively.

Discussion of Findings

This study using descriptive and inferential statistical methods; the Spearman Rank Order Correlation tool and at a 95% confidence interval, investigated the relationship between Reverse Logistics and Customer Referral of paint manufacturing firms in Rivers State. The findings revealed a significant and positive relationship between Reverse Logistics and Customer Referral of paint manufacturing firms in Port Harcourt. The findings of this study confirmed previous studies by Bilqis et. al. (2019) explores reverse logistics activities such as product return, reuse of materials, and waste disposal impacts on the management of waste products in the Nigerian manufacturing companies. Customers appreciated the ease and efficiency of returns, which contributed to higher repeat business and stronger brand allegiance Their findings revealed that reverse logistics activities arising from return of goods may be very important in the development of efficient and effective management of waste products in Nigeria manufacturing firms. The results also indicated that reverse logistics is highly significant in achieving organizational goals, company's future success, the functioning of a manufacturing company and strategically positioning of the company. Also, Schmidt & Bauer (2017) empirically carried out a study on the Influence of Reverse Logistics on Consumer Trust and Satisfaction of paint manufacturing firms in Rivers State and reveal reverse logistics practices were positively associated with higher levels of consumer trust and satisfaction, as they demonstrated reliability and responsiveness in handling returns.

The Relationship Between product return and customer Referral

The positive value of 3.3895 shows the strength of the relationships between product return and customer Referral. The P-value (0.00) is less than the level of significance at (0.05). Hence, this suggests that a positive relationship exists between product return and customer Referral. Supporting the above is the work of Lemon. (2017) conducted a study on the impact of returned policies on customer satisfaction and loyalty. The research adopted a mixed-method study involving both quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews. The study found that lenient return policies, such as no-questions-asked returns, product replacement and extended return windows, significantly enhanced customer satisfaction and loyalty. Customers valued the flexibility and security these policies provided, leading to increased trust in the retailer.

Furthermore, Nguyen (2018) conducted a study to investigate customer expectations and perceptions of fairness in return processes and found that key aspects influencing perceptions included clarity of return policies, ease of the return process and the respect shown by customer service representatives. The research conducted a cross-sectional survey of customers from various retail backgrounds. The survey assessed customer expectations before making a return and their perceptions of the fairness and transparency of the return process, the findings revealed that Customers who perceived the return process as fair and transparent reported higher satisfaction levels. Again, Lemon. (2017) conducted a study on the impact of return policies on customer satisfaction and loyalty. The study found that lenient return policies, such as no-questions-asked returns and extended return windows, significantly enhanced customer satisfaction and loyalty. Customers valued the flexibility and security these policies provided, leading to increased trust in the retailer.

The relationship between Recycling and Customer Referral

The positive value of 3.0877 shows the strength of the relationships between Recycling and Customer Referral. The P-value (0.00) is less than the level of significance at (0.05). Therefore, this suggests that a positive relationship exists between Recycling and Customer Referral. Supporting this result is the work of Gonçalves and Silva (2020) whose study found that municipalities that provided detailed information about recycling processes and made recycling more accessible experienced a significant increase in customer satisfaction. Also, Li and Zhang (2019) concluded that the

convenience and ease of use of recycling facilities directly contribute to a positive shopping experience and overall customer satisfaction. Again, Yang & Johnson (2017). Conducted a study on the impact of Recycling Practices on Customer Satisfaction in the Hospitality Industry, examined how different waste management strategies influenced customer satisfaction in hotels and restaurants. The study suggests that integrating sustainable waste practices can serve as a differentiator in competitive hospitality markets.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was ascertained that Reverse Logistics plays a major role in the minds of customers in regard with of Paint Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State. This study shows relative importance of the relationship between Reverse Logistics and Customer Satisfaction leading to customer referral. This study concludes that if Paint Manufacturing firms want to enjoy good profits globally stemming from positive referrals, it should work hard to increase customer satisfaction by enhancing positive customer experience for every product returned and effective product recycling in the market place.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Paint manufacturing firms in Rivers State should account for the importance of providing good customer experience for reverse logistics if they want their customers remain loyal to their products.
2. The company should make deliberate steps that would give extra value to the customers. This would make the customer satisfied with the company's products.
3. Customers seek respected attitude from the company, paint manufacturing companies should strive for Positive word of mouth for every experience with customers.

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